

Design and Manufacture of an Industrial Low Cost Pick-and-Place Parallel Mechanism

Ünsal Dinçer, DALAN Kimya Endüstri A.Ş., Kemalpaşa Cad. No.325 35060 Pınarbaşı İzmir, Türkiye
Mehmet Çevik*, İzmir Katip Çelebi Univ., Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Çiğli Main Campus, İzmir, Türkiye
*Corresponding author: mehmet.cevik@ikc.edu.tr

Abstract

A low-cost parallel mechanism that meets with the expectations of industry was designed and prototyped rapidly within domestic manufacturing capabilities. The manufacturing cost of this manipulator is about one third of a similar commercial manipulator in the market and will decrease significantly in subsequent productions.

Keywords: parallel mechanism, kinematic, servo, Codesys

Discipline: Mechatronics Engineering

INTRODUCTION

The aim of this study is to design and manufacture an industrial low cost parallel mechanism to be used in Dalan Kimya Soap Manufacturing Plant for quality control, and pick and place of soaps. The cost of parallel manipulators is an important aspect in their design and implementation in the industry. In the last decade, there are various studies about manufacturing low cost parallel robots in the literature. Cazalilla et al. [1] designed a low cost parallel-robot PRS that has been controlled using Oroco modules. Orocos is a real-time middleware focused on control systems. The authors mention its advantage as the capability to provide an off-the-shelf hard real-time operation, which is crucial in most of the robotics applications. Grajewski et al. [2] presented new approach to creating interactive simulations for testing tactile interaction with the user, which involves use of a low-cost device. They used a parallel kinematic structure (Delta robot) for this purpose. According to the authors, this type of application will be able in the future to support the effectiveness of virtual training, with particular emphasis on educational simulation. Another low cost and robust robot design study is carried out by Gomez et al. [3]. It is a tool for students to gain experience integrating different mechatronic fields of knowledge, as well as practicing the procedures needed to successfully accomplish their own design. Ottavino et al. [4] presented the design and kinematic performances for a low-cost parallel manipulator with 4 driven cables. A prototype has been built and tests have experienced the feasibility of the system design and its operation. The ability to work in an unexplored environment is crucial to the success of the autonomous robot's operation. The simultaneous localization and mapping is a technique used to build a map of the robot's surrounding while keeping track of its position. In recent years, significant attention has been paid to the development of this technique. One of the reasons behind this popularity is the low price [5]. A group of researchers developed a low cost parallel robot to assist impaired persons in making 3-dof movements of the forearm and wrist with a parts and machining cost of less than 1500 USD. The process of design and development of a low cost small sized in-pipe inspection robot was examined in another study [7]. Some researches focused on low cost robot parts. Gutiérrez et al. [8] manufactured a prototype of a lightweight robot arm with a low cost budget, fully functional. They used their prototype to test and fix elements for driving and controlling. They concluded some recommendations about material, reinforcements, geometry of the parts as a result of their investigation. Another research [9] is about the design of a robot gripper for a service robot that moves rapidly. The required criteria were light weight, low cost and friendly shape.

As can be concluded from these studies, there is still interest to develop low cost manipulators. The present study focuses on such a research. Custom-made parts, two servomotors, a control unit and open source code available to everyone have a much lower cost than their counterparts have in the market.

MECHANICAL DESIGN

According to preliminary inspections of manufacturing lines, the workspace required for pick and place process was determined. The total degrees of freedom of the manipulator is calculated as 2. The solid model of a new mechanism was designed via Solidworks software through inspiration of existing

two degrees-of-freedom parallel mechanisms. The kinematic equations were derived and forward and inverse kinematics solutions were obtained using Matlab software, the sign analysis was performed; then the maximum available workspace of the mechanism was drawn. The equations were verified by comparing the results obtained by Solidworks and Matlab programs. Figure 1 displays the motion analysis in Solidworks.

Figure 1. Motion analysis in Solidworks.

The maximal working space in the XZ-plane and the physical constraints are shown in Figure 2. An optimum working area, based on trajectory and general requirements, was determined within the maximal workspace that was determined considering the physical constraints.

Figure 2. The maximal working space and the physical constraints.

The maximum and minimum values of joint angles, within the specified workspace, were calculated. These values were input in the servo program software.

Trajectories were generated within the specified workspace and motion analysis was carried out by Matlab and Solidworks software. The trajectory of the moving platform is determined using the widely used cubic polynomials. The advantage of spline interpolation is that it tends to greatly reduce oscillation between data points. Cubic spline interpolation gives a good approximation over the whole interval. Figure 3 illustrates the trajectory planning using cubic polynomials with via points.

Figure 3. Trajectory planning using cubic polynomials with via points.

Upon the determination of the trajectory, position, velocity and acceleration profiles are analyzed. The required torque value in the rotary actuators were determined and an appropriate servo motor was selected accordingly. The static and transient structural analyses were performed to assess the mechanical stresses of mechanism under load condition.

MANUFACTURING

After completing the inverse and forward analyses in Matlab and verifying, the prototype is manufactured. In prototype manufacturing, some parts of mechanism were manufactured by waterjet cutting process to prevent the heating. Other parts were machined on lathe, milling and CNC within defined tolerances.

Figure 4. Material type codes of the parts of mechanism.

The materials used in manufacturing are given in Figure 4 and Table 1.

Table 1. Materials used in manufacturing the manipulator

Material	Code
AISI 1050 Carbon steel	a
7Aluminum alloy 7075	b
Carbon Fiber 3K	c
16MnCr5 - Case Hardening Steel	d

Other mechanical components used in manufacturing are lightweight, maintenance free, dry-running, polymeric spherical joint with chemical resistance and high fatigue strength, and high precision, maintenance-free, low heat planet reducer. They are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Other mechanical components (left: joint, right: planet-reducer)

The Schneider brand BSH series industrial servo motors with a holding torque of 1.4 Nm are used as rotary actuator (Figure 6). This motor is selected by calculating the required moment according to the Solidworks motion analysis. Schneider brand LMC58 motion controller and Lexi32 series servo drive are utilized. The Beijer operator panel is used as the human-machine interface for remote control and adjustment of the mechanism.

Figure 6. Schneider BSH servomotor

The forward and inverse kinematic solutions and trajectory planning codes derived from Matlab, were transferred to the servo software (Codesys). Final verification of motion planning is performed by a simple five-bar mechanism constructed on a frame (Figure 7) instead of actual prototype.

Figure 7. The five bar mechanism and the frame.

After the final verification process, original prototype (Figure 8) has been assembled on the frame.

Figure 8. Final view of the original prototype

The cost of all the materials, handwork, servomotors, control units and other components used in the prototype are about one third of a similar commercial manipulator in the market. It is obvious that the cost will decrease significantly in subsequent productions, approximately to one-fourth or less of a similar commercial one.

While the parallel mechanism is designed for soap industry, it can be modified easily to be utilized in other industries and with different dimensions. The software used is compatible with brand independent IEC 61131-3 standard and Codesys platform, and adaptable with all motion control units using Codesys.

CONCLUSION

As a result of this study, a low-cost parallel mechanism that meets with the expectations of industry was designed and prototyped rapidly within domestic manufacturing capabilities. All the necessary analysis is carried out with high precision. The cost of all the materials, handwork, servomotors, control units and other components used in the prototype are about one third of a similar commercial manipulator in the market. It is obvious that the cost will decrease significantly in subsequent productions, approximately to one-fourth or less of a similar commercial one.

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